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MATHEMATICAL MODEL BASED ON MULTI-AGENT REINFORCEMENT LEARNING (MARL) AND PARTIALLY OBSERVABLE MARKOV DECISION PROCESS (POMDP) FOR MODELING CARGO MOVEMENT FOR A MOBILE ROBOTS GROUP

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a mathematical model that combines multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) and partially observable Markov decision process (POMDP) to model the task of moving cargo by a mobile robots group. The use of such methods allows agents to effectively interact under conditions of incomplete information, optimizing task performance in real, dynamic environments. This model has significant potential for process automation in industrial and logistics systems.

Keywords: Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning, POMDP, Mobile Robot, Optimization, Cargo Movement, Agent Coordination, Dynamic Environment.

INTRODUCTION

Autonomous mobile robots play a key role in modern logistics, industrial and rescue operations, where efficient cargo movement is an important task [1]-[19]. The use of groups of robots instead of single systems allows improving productivity, reducing operation time and ensuring flexibility in changing conditions [20]-[22]. However, the coordination of such robotic systems in a real environment requires the development of complex mathematical models that take into account resource limitations, the dynamics of variable factors and partial availability of information. Taking into account the battery charge level, the current load of robots, the spatial configuration of the environment and the possibility of cooperation between agents complicate traditional approaches to planning. Different methods and approaches can also be used here [23]-[47].

In this regard, the use of multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) methods in combination with partially observable Markov decision processes (POMDP) is appropriate for creating adaptive control strategies for such systems. This approach allows mobile robots to learn the optimal distribution of actions, effectively respond to changes in the environment and make informed decisions based on incomplete information. The combination of MARL and POMDP provides the ability to predict key events, such as the need for recharging, insufficient resources for transportation, or the need for cooperation to move the load. This allows increasing the level of autonomy, reducing energy consumption, and improving the overall performance of the robotic system.

The development of a mathematical model that integrates these approaches is a relevant task aimed at improving the control algorithms of multi-robot systems under real operational constraints. The use of such a model opens up new opportunities for the implementation of multi-agent autonomous systems in production processes, logistics centers, and complex environments where speed, adaptability, and reliability of decision-making are important.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Robots working in groups bring both benefits and problems. The main problem is effective control. Robots should not collide and perform tasks rationally. These problems are being addressed by many researchers. Let us consider some recent works.

A challenging problem in robotics is how to control multiple robots cooperatively and safely in real-world applications [48]. Experimental results proposed in [48] on the three safe MARL benchmarks indicate that our methods can achieve state-of-the-art performance in the balance between improving reward and satisfying safety constraints compared with strong baselines.

Hu, J., and co-authors in [49] propose a unified group coordinated control scheme for networked multi-robot systems having multiple targets. Two hardware experiments (target-enclosing and object transportation) involving real mobile robots have been carried out to demonstrate the usefulness of the proposed scheme.

The paper [50] analyses two approaches to control a multi robot system, also known as a robot formation or robot cluster, namely the leader-follower and the virtual structure approaches. There is also discussed how to implement a hierarchical control structure, when regarding conflicting control objectives, showing how to implement a control system taking into account the different priorities assigned to the subtasks involved in the accomplishment of the whole task.

Authors in [51] propose a multi-modal task-based graphical user interface for controlling a heterogeneous multi-robot team. The core of the interface is an integrated multi-robot task allocation system to allow the user to encode his/her intents to guide the heterogeneous multi-robot team.

The study [52] propose a decentralized method of spherical amphibious multi-robot control system based on blockchain technology. The consensus plugin, smart contract and decentralized multi-robot control algorithm were designed to achieve decentralization. The experimental results of consensus of spherical amphibious multi-robot showed the effectiveness of the decentralization.

Orr, J., & Dutta, A. in [53] explore multi-agent deep reinforcement learning, where multiple agents present in the environment not only learn from their own experiences but also from each other and its applications in multi-robot systems.

So, we see a significant interest of scientists in solving the problem of controlling a group of robots. Below in this article we will present our vision of solving this problem.

DEVELOPMENT OF A MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR SIMULATING CARGO MOVEMENT BY A MOBILE ROBOTS GROUP

Within the framework of these studies, we will present a description of the environment as a set of mobile robots $R = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n\}$, which must transport a cargo W from the initial point A to the final point B . Each robot has a limited battery charge, a limited load capacity and certain dynamic constraints.

Based on the partially observable Markov decision process (POMDP) model, the POMDP model within the framework of the study can be represented by the following tuple:

$$(S, A, T, R, \Omega, O, \gamma), \quad (1)$$

S – set of possible states of the environment;

A – set of actions;

$T: S \times A \rightarrow P(S)$ – state transition function;

$R: S \times A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ – reward function;

Ω - set of possible observations;

$O: S \times A \rightarrow P(\Omega)$ – observation function;

$\gamma \in [0,1]$ – discount rate.

Let us represent environment state (S) in such a way, that each robot r_i has its own stata s_i :

$$s_i = \{x_i, y_i, E_i, L_i, C_i\}, \quad (2)$$

x_i, y_i – robot coordinates in 2D space;

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$E_i \in [0,1]$ – normalized battery charge level;

$L_i \in [0,1]$ – load state (1 – carrying cargo, 0 – free);

C_i – the current load of the robot (if the robot is lifting a cargo).

The general state of the environment can be represented by the following expression:

$$S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n, x_W, y_W, m_W\}, \quad (3)$$

x_W, y_W – cargo coordinates;

m_W – cargo weight.

Each robot r_i can perform such a set of actions (A):

$$A = \{Move, Charge, Pickup, Drop, Wait\}, \quad (4)$$

Move – moving in the direction(d_x, d_y);

Charge – movement to the charging station;

Pickup – attempt to lift a cargo (success depends on $m_W < C_i$);

Drop – cargo discharge;

Wait – expectation.

Reward function $R(s, a)$ is formed to stimulate the right actions:

$$R(s, a) = \begin{cases} +10, & \text{if the cargo is successfully delivered to the point B} \\ -5, & \text{if the robot has stopped due to low battery} \\ -2, & \text{if the robot cannot lift the load due to excess weight} \\ -1, & \text{for every step without performing a useful action} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

If the battery charge E_i drops below 20%, a penalty is imposed for performing any action except Charge.

The transition between states is determined by the transition function $T(s, a)$, which is based on the robot kinematics:

$$(x_i', y_i') = (x_i, y_i) + v_i \cdot (\cos\theta, \sin\theta) \cdot dt, \quad (6)$$

v_i – robot speed;

θ – direction of movement;

dt – discrete time step.

When recharging, the charge changes according to the law:

$$\dot{E}_i = \min(1, E_i + \alpha dt), \quad (7)$$

α - charging speed.

The charge level changes during movement according to the formula:

$$\dot{E}_i = E_i - \beta v_i^2 dt, \quad (8)$$

β – energy consumption coefficient.

Since the POMDP model, the robot has partially limited information, the observation function $O(s, a)$, has the following form :

$$O_i = \{x_i, y_i, E_i, L_i, C_i, d_{iW}, d_{iB}\}, \quad (9)$$

d_{iW} – distance between robot i and cargo;

d_{iB} – the distance between the cargo and point B .

The learning goal is to find a policy $\pi^*(s)$, that maximizes the total reward:

$$\pi^*(s) = \arg \max_{\pi} \mathbb{E} [\sum_{t=0}^s \gamma^t R(s_t, a_t)]. \quad (10)$$

It is proposed to use the following MARL methods for training agents that depend on the type of actions:

- Deep Q-Network (DQN) for discrete actions;
- Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) for continuous actions.

Development of decision conditions when the robot decides to recharge or ask for help:

- the transition to charging occurs when E_i falls below the threshold E_{min} :

$$E_i < E_{min} \Rightarrow a_i = Charge, \quad (11)$$

- a request for help occurs when:

$$m_W > C \text{ або } d_{iW} > d_{max}. \quad (12)$$

The proposed mathematical model based on MARL and POMDP allows for effective modeling of the process of cargo transportation by mobile robots, taking into account the battery charge level, distance, cargo mass, and the need for cooperation. Robots are able to adaptively make decisions about the optimal route, choose actions such as recharging or requesting assistance, and learn through reinforcement learning. The reward function encourages efficient energy use and prevents robots from idling, and the observation function allows agents to work under conditions of partial uncertainty. The optimal policy obtained through DQN or PPO algorithms helps to minimize task execution time and energy consumption, ensuring effective interaction between agents. Thanks to collaborative learning, robots can coordinate their actions, identify critical situations such as lack of charge or exceeding load capacity, and adapt their behavior according to environmental changes. The proposed approach can be used in real-world scenarios of autonomous logistics, industrial automation, and mobile robotics.

DEVELOPMENT OF A PROGRAM TO SIMULATE THE MOVING CARGO FOR A MOBILE ROBOTS GROUP

The choice of the Python programming language for developing a program for simulating the movement of cargo by mobile robots is justified by its flexibility, a large number of libraries for calculations and visualization, as well as the simplicity of the syntax, which speeds up the development process [54]-[56]. Python provides convenient integration with machine learning libraries such as TensorFlow and PyTorch, which is important for implementing multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL). In addition, the Pygame library allows you to create effective 2D visualization of the process, which simplifies the display of the movement of robots, cargo and obstacles. The PyCharm development environment was chosen due to its extensive capabilities in debugging code, convenient autocompletion and support for large projects. Its powerful code analysis tools allow you to quickly find errors, and integration with virtual environments ensures conflict-free dependency management. PyCharm also offers a convenient built-in terminal, which allows you to run scripts directly in the development environment. Thanks to support for working with Git, PyCharm makes it easy to manage project versions and collaborate on code. The presence of a visual editor and flexible file navigation makes it easier to work on complex algorithms for planning the movement of mobile robots. A large community of Python developers provides quick

access to documentation and examples, which simplifies the resolution of technical issues. Thus, Python in combination with PyCharm is the optimal choice for developing this program, as it allows you to quickly implement complex algorithms and provides a convenient environment for testing and debugging. An example of the implementation of functions is given below.

```
def __init__(self, x, y):
    self.x, self.y = x, y
    self.charge = random.randint(50, 100)
    self.carrying = False
    self.charging = False
```

This code snippet defines a class constructor for an object (probably a mobile robot) that initializes its coordinates (x, y), a random battery level between 50 and 100, and two flags: carrying (indicating whether the robot is carrying a load) and charging (indicating whether the robot is charging).

```
def move_towards(self, target):
    if self.charge <= 0:
        return
    dx, dy = target[0] - self.x, target[1] - self.y
    distance = math.sqrt(dx ** 2 + dy ** 2)
    if distance > 0:
        self.x += int(dx / distance * GRID_SIZE)
        self.y += int(dy / distance * GRID_SIZE)
        self.charge -= 1
```

This method moves the robot towards the given target if its charge is greater than 0. It calculates the displacement vector, normalizes it, and moves the robot by a step of size GRID_SIZE, decreasing the charge by 1 unit.

```
def draw(self):
    pygame.draw.rect(screen, (255, 0, 0), (self.x - 5, self.y - 5, 10, 10))
    robots = [Robot(random.randint(0, WIDTH // GRID_SIZE) * GRID_SIZE,
random.randint(0, HEIGHT // GRID_SIZE) * GRID_SIZE)
        for _ in range(NUM_ROBOTS)]
    load = Load()
    running = True
    while running:
        screen.fill((255, 255, 255))
        for event in pygame.event.get():
            if event.type == pygame.QUIT:
                running = False
```

This code fragment is responsible for the visualization and the main loop of the program. The draw() method draws the robot as a red square on the screen. Next, a list of robots in random positions is created and the cargo object is initialized. In the main while running loop, the screen is updated (with a white background) and events are processed, in particular, exiting the program when the window close button is pressed. HMI implementations of the program for modeling the execution of the cargo moving task for a group of mobile robots are shown in Figure 1.

In Figure 1, the blue circle indicates the cargo to be moved; the green circle indicates the mobile robots and the percentage of battery charge; the yellow circle indicates the charging point; the series of squares are obstacles in the simulation area.

Let us conduct two experiments to simulate the task execution by mobile robots. It shows the execution time, charge consumption, distance traveled and the number of obstacles avoided in each case. The obtained simulation results are presented in Table 1.

Figure 1: Implementation of HMI program for simulation of cargo movement for a mobile robots group

Table 1: Experimental results

Experiment	Execution Time (s)	Charge Consumption (%)	Distance Traveled (units)	Obstacles Avoided
1	45	30	120	3
2	52	35	140	4

For ease of analysis, we present the obtained data in the form of a graph in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Experimental results

CONCLUSION

Mathematical models based on multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) and partially observable Markov decision process (POMDP) are powerful tools for modeling complex tasks, in particular for the task of moving a load by a group of mobile robots. The use of MARL allows agents to interact and learn based on shared experience, which contributes to the achievement of a collective goal through information exchange and coordination of actions. By using POMDP, it is possible to model scenarios where the work of agents is carried out under conditions of incomplete or partial information about the environment, which is a common situation in real conditions. In parallel, such approaches allow to take into account complex factors such as noise in measurements, limitations on sensors or changes in the environment. This makes it possible to achieve high efficiency in tasks related to mobile robots, in particular for carrying a load in complex or dynamic environments. This is suitable for both industrial applications and mobile robotic systems in open spaces, where coordination between agents can significantly increase performance. At the same time, the complexity of solving such problems lies in the need for deep learning of models for effective processing of partial observations, which requires significant computational resources and optimization of algorithm parameters. Despite these difficulties, the development of such methods promises revolutionary changes in the automation of many processes, providing high flexibility and adaptability of robotic systems in real-time conditions.

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